

Appendix B

The goals, challenges and it's KPIs

Goals	Goals KPIs	Challenges	Challenges KPIs
Clean streets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of citizens' complaints per month • The Number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters • Your KPI name 	Not enough trash cans Streets not cleaned often enough by janitors Low level of environmental awareness among residents Insufficiently frequent of garbage trucks movement Poor cleanliness of the area around waste containers Overflow of waste containers Birds scattering garbage	-
Clean public places, such as parks, car parks or shopping areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of citizens' complaints per month • The Number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters • Your KPI name 	Not enough trash cans Public places not cleaned often enough by janitors Low level of environmental awareness among residents Insufficiently frequent of garbage trucks movement Poor cleanliness of the area around waste containers Overflow of waste containers Birds scattering garbage	-
Improve the environmental situation in the city	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of citizens' complaints per month • Your KPI name 	Air quality Garbage on the streets Garbage in public places Unauthorized garbage dumps Insufficiently frequent of garbage trucks movement Hazardous waste is not sorted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air Quality Index • Number of citizens' complaints per month • The Number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters • Number of citizens' complaints per month • The Number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters • Number of citizens' complaints per month • Number of citizens' complaints per month • Kilograms of sorted hazardous waste per month
Budget savings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total costs (€) • Saved costs (€) • Your KPI name 	Garbage collection with garbage trucks (gasoline, drivers' salaries) Janitor salaries Waste sorting costs Waste processing costs Waste disposal costs	-
Improving the waste management logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of citizens' complaints per month • Number of rides per month • Your KPI name 	Garbage is taken out irregularly Empty runs Garbage trucks obstruct traffic Different types of garbage are collected by different companies	-
Increasing stakeholder awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of stakeholders Awareness and Engagement in Waste Management activities (1-Unaware, 2- Resistant, 3- Neutral, 4- Supportive, 5- Leading) • Your KPI name 	Waste collection company (Drivers) Waste collection company (Dispatchers) Janitors Authorities / City administration / District administration Waste department Waste disposal organization Waste recycling company Waste treating company Waste storage organization	-
Introduction / improvement of waste processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of waste processed per month • Your KPI name 	Lack of infrastructure Incorrect waste sorting	-
Improvement of bio-waste processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of bio-waste processed in the city per month 	Lack of infrastructure	-

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Your KPI name 	Incorrect waste sorting	
Cost effective technology solutions for SWM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs saved per month (€) Your KPI name 	Household waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs saved per month (€) Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Household waste logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs saved per month (€) Number of citizens' complaints per month Number of empty runs per month
		Household waste sorting of bio-waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs saved per month (€) Number of kg of bio-waste sorted correctly per month
		Household waste logistics of bio-waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs saved per month (€) Number of citizens' complaints per month Number of empty runs per month Smell, numeric (Data from gas / air quality sensor)
		Air quality	-
		Waste processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs saved per month (€) Number of kg of waste processed per month
		Citizens awareness, engagement and motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs saved per month (€) Number of kg of each type of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
Increase the waste recycling level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Your KPI name 	Lack of infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of each type of waste recycled per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) Number of kg of each type of waste per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Incorrect waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of each type of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Problems with citizens participation in waste reduction, recycling, other sustainable WM practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of participants in WM practices per month
		Problems with citizens willingness to pay for new sustainable WM services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amount of payments per month (€)
Electronical waste (E-waste) sorting and disposal improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of e-waste sorted correctly per month Your KPI name 	Making e-waste sorting and disposal easier and accessible	-
		Incorrect e-waste sorting	
		Low citizens motivation	
Improving the logistics and way of operation regarding bio-waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month Smell, numeric (Data from gas / air quality sensor) Your KPI name 	Bio-waste is taken out irregularly	-
		Smell	
		Spread of diseases due to untimely disposal of waste	
Waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of each type of waste per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, 	Sorting of household waste: Incorrect waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton,

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	Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Your KPI name		Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of kg of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Sorting of household waste: Residents do not sort all types of garbage	• Number of kg of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Introduction of sorting of more types of waste	• Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of waste types sorted in each district of the city
Waste minimization	• Number of kg of each type of waste per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Your KPI name	Low citizens motivation Low citizens awareness	
Increasing environmental awareness, engagement and motivation of citizens	• Level of stakeholders Awareness, Motivation and Engagement in Waste Management activities (1- Unaware, 2- Resistant, 3- Neutral, 4- Supportive, 5- Leading) • Your KPI name	Incorrect household waste sorting Residents do not sort all types of garbage Residence do not sort waste at all Garbage on the streets Garbage in public places Garbage storage is far away from home Don't get enough knowledge/education of waste sorting Takes extra time and effort to sort waste properly Lack of awareness of how excess waste affects negatively on the environmental and human wellbeing	• Number of kg of each type of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of citizens' complaints per month • The Number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters • Number of citizens' complaints per month • The Number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of citizens' complaints per month • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)

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		Lack of information on points for separate collection of some types of waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of citizens' complaints per month
		Lack of information on the rules for waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Problems with citizens participation in waste reduction, recycling, other sustainable WM practices	-
		Problems with citizens' willingness to pay for new sustainable WM services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amount of payments per month (€)